

1160 cm^{-1} , and ν phenolic OH at 3300-3400 cm^{-1}).

where R=H, 4-methyl pyrimidyl, 4,6-dimethyl pyrimidyl or (N'-2-thiazolyl sulphonilamido).

R'=H, CH_3 , COOH

R''=H, COO_2H_3

Experimental

α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3,5-dichloro benzal anils/2-benzoate^{1,3}: 2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichloro benzophenone^{1,4} (0.01 M) dissolved in ethanol, was added to sulphanilamide (0.01 M) in ethanol and refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The contents were poured into water. The product thus isolated was crystallised from ethanol. The anils were benzoylated by treatment with benzoylchloride and 10% cold sodium hydroxide solution. The product poured on ice, extracted with solvent ether, and crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

2-Phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dichloro phenyl)-3-N-aminosulphophenyl/4-methyl pyrimidyl/4,6-dimethyl pyrimidyl/3(N'-2-thiazolyl sulphonilamido)-5-H/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone and their benzoyl derivative: α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3,5-dichlorobenzal anils/2-benzoate (0.01 M in dry benzene) was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.01 M) on a water bath for 4 hr. The product thus separated was crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-(2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dichloro phenyl)-3-M-amino sulphophenyl/4-methyl pyrimidyl/4,6-dimethyl pyrimidyl/3CN'-2-thiazolyl sulphonilamido/-5-H/-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones and their benzoyl derivative^{1,5}: α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3,5-dichlorobenzal anils (0.01 M) were condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 M) in presence of zinc chloride (0.5 g) for 2 hr at 160° (Reddelien method^{1,6}). The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated by 10% hydrochloric acid, crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

Antimicrobial screening: The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup plate³ method using *S. aureus* and *E. coli* as test organism. The testing was carried out in DMF solution. The difference between the zone of inhibitions of the test solution and pure solvent (DMF) are recored in Tables 1 and 2.

All compounds are highly active against *S. aureus*. In case of anils, where R=H, 4-methyl pyrimidyl and R'=H, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}$, the compound possess good activity while in case of 4-thiazolidinones where R=H, N'-2-thiazolyl sulphonilamido, R'=H and R''=H, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}$ the compounds possess good activity.

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Synthesis of 10-Arylidene Anthrones

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THOUGH a lot of work has been reported on anthrone, not much attention has been given to its reactive methylene group. 10-Arylidene anthrones were synthesised by reacting the corresponding 10-anthranyl triphenyl phosphonium, or arsonium yelides with aryl aldehydes¹. Only one direct synthesis of *m*-nitrobenzylidene anthrone was reported² by condensing anthrone with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in piperidine and pyridine base using xylene as a solvent.

It was, therefore, thought of interest to study the reactivity of methylene group. Two methods were followed in the condensation reactions. In one, anthrone was condensed with aryl aldehyde in the presence of acetic anhydride containing a few drops of piperidine base and in the other, alcohol was used as a solvent with a few drops of piperidine base.

Experimental

The m.p.s were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The structures are supported by elemental analysis and spectral data. UV spectra

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Ar	Solvent		m.p. °C	Yield%		M.F.	Analysis% Found/(Calcd.)	
		Ac	Alc		Ac	Alc		C	H
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	Ac	Alc	124	50	73	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O	89.9 (89.36)	5.1 (4.965)
2.	p-NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ -	..	..	181	60	80.0	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ ON	77.04 (77.06)	3.97 (3.91)
3.	C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	..	..	112	—	60	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O	77.1 (77.06)	3.99 (3.97)
4.	p-CH ₃ O - C ₆ H ₄ -	..	..	282	—	70	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₂	84.66 (84.61)	5.16 (5.12)
5.	o-HO - C ₆ H ₄ -	..	..	232	45	—	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	84.5 (84.56)	4.9 (4.7)

Ac—Acetic anhydride; Alc—Alcohol

(λ_{max} in nm) were recorded in methanol, ir spectra (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) in KBr pellets and nmr (chemical shifts in δ_{ppm}) using TMS as a standard.

Preparation of 10-arylidene anthrone (Table I): Equimolar quantities of anthrone and suitably substituted aldehydes (0.001 mole) were taken in acetic anhydride (20-25 ml) with 2-3 drops of piperidine. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 hr, poured into cold saturated NaHCO₃ solution, filtered, and washed with water. The solid was then dried and crystallised from suitable solvents. In the second method an identical procedure was followed except that in place of acetic anhydride alcohol was used as the solvent: uv 368; ir 1655 ($>C=O$), 1595 ($>C=C$); nmr 7.1 (s, $>C=C$), 7.4–8.23 (m, Ar-H).

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Rare Flavone-C-Glycosides from

Mollugo cerviana

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THE genus *Mollugo* included till recently in the betalin family Aizoaceae¹, has been separated and taken into the new anthocyanin family Molluginaceae² in the same order, Centrospermae. As a part of chemotaxonomic studies on *Mollugo*, we

have screened³ the flavonoid constituents of six *Mollugo* species (*M. disticha*, *M. pentaphylla*, *M. nudicaulis*, *M. cerviana*, *M. lotoides* and *M. oppositifolia*) and found that all of them contained flavone-C-glycosides and were devoid of 6-oxygenated flavones. In continuation of our report on the occurrence of new flavone-C-glycosides in *M. disticha*³ and *M. pentaphylla*⁴, we present here the isolation and characterisation of four flavone-C-glycosides including two rare ones (orientin-2''-O-glucoside and vitexin-2''-O-glucoside) from *M. cerviana*.

Experimental

Fresh whole plants of *M. cerviana* were collected from Pondicherry and worked up for flavonoids according to standard procedures³⁻⁵. The flavone-C-glycosides extracted from the aqueous alcoholic concentrate by partition with ethyl methyl ketone or butanol were subjected to three-stage separation (column chromatography over silica, preparative paper chromatography and thin layer chromatography over silica) to yield four tlc homogeneous compounds, A–D, which were studied by uv fluorescence, colour reactions, λ_{max} , m.p., R_f , products of acid hydrolysis and characterised as follows.

Compound A: Yellow crystals, m.p. 265–67°; R_f : 30, 48(PC, 15% HOAc, BAW); λ_{max} : 255, 265, 345(MeOH); 270, 275, 325sh, 385(NaOAc) and 275, 300sh, 335sh, 425(AlCl₃); unaffected by acid hydrolysis; ir (KBr): superimposable to the spectrum of authentic luteolin-8-C-glucoside (orientin). Identity as orientin⁶ confirmed by co-tlc (R_f : 71, 60; silica gel; ethyl acetate, ethyl methyl ketone, formic acid, water = 5 : 3 : 1 : 1; ethyl acetate, methanol, water = 63 : 12 : 9) with an authentic sample.

Compound B: Light yellow needles, m.p. 250–52°; R_f : 32, 51(PC, 15% HOAc, BAW); λ_{max} : 270, 300 sh, 335(MeOH); 280, 300 sh, 370(NaOAc) and 280, 305, 345, 385(AlCl₃); unaffected by acid